

PORTABILITY OF APPLICATIONS TO HETEROGENEOUS SYSTEMS AND EXASCALE

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The Exascale area is here

- Pre-Exascale Systems [Aggregate Linpack (Rmax) = 323 PF!]

Which scientific domains are those systems serving?

How science drives architectures

<i>Algorithm Science areas</i>	<i>Dense linear algebra</i>	<i>Sparse linear algebra</i>	<i>Spectral Methods (FFT)</i>	<i>Particle Methods</i>	<i>Structured Grids</i>	<i>Unstructured or AMR Grids</i>	<i>Data Intensive</i>
Accelerator Science		X	X	X	X	X	
Astrophysics	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Chemistry	X	X	X	X			X
Climate			X		X	X	X
Combustion					X	X	X
Fusion	X	X		X	X	X	X
Lattice Gauge		X	X	X	X		
Material Science	X		X	X	X		

<i>Algorithm Science areas</i>	<i>Dense linear algebra</i>	<i>Sparse linear algebra</i>	<i>Spectral Methods (FFT)s</i>	<i>Particle Methods</i>	<i>Structured Grids</i>	<i>Unstructured or AMR Grids</i>	<i>Data Intensive</i>
Accelerator Science		High performance memory system		High performance memory system			
Astrophysics			High bisection bandwidth			Low latency, efficient gather /scatter	Storage, Network Infrastructure
Chemistry	High Flop/s rate				High flop/s rate		
Climate							
Combustion							
Fusion	High Flop/s rate						
Lattice Gauge							
Material Science							

Current and Emerging Systems

NERSC Perlmutter
AMD CPU / NVIDIA GPU
CUDA

ORNL Frontier
AMD CPU / AMD GPU
HIP

ANL Aurora
Intel CPU / Intel GPU
DPC++

LLNL El Capitan
AMD CPU / AMD GPU
HIP

- Multiple vendors **and** programming models across systems
- How does one support **all** systems?

Research Challenges & Question

- Current and emerging HPC systems feature increasingly larger per-node accelerator/core/thread counts
- Greater attention to thread scalability required for efficient node use
- Increasing diversity among HPC systems makes portable codebases desirable
- **Can current programming models and performance portability layers (PPLs) support such systems?**

Programming models

- HIP / CUDA
- OpenMP
- OpenACC
- MPI+X
- Kokkos
- SYCL

What is the X in MPI-X ?

✓ OpenMP is about 50%, out of all choices of X

Courtesy of Yun (Helen) He, Alice Koniges, et. al., (NERSC) at OpenMPCon'2015

Kokkos

- C++ library enabling portable, thread-scalable code optimized for CPU, GPU, and MIC architectures
 - *Back-ends to models such as CUDA, OpenMP, HIP*
- Provides abstractions to control:
 - *how/where kernels are executed,*
 - *where data is allocated, and*
 - *how data is mapped to memory*
- Enables performance portability
 - *Developers remain responsible for writing performant code*

Capabilities

	Implementation Technique	Parallel Loops	Parallel Reduction	Tightly Nested Loops	Non-tightly Nested Loops	Task Parallelism	Data Allocations	Data Transfers	Advanced Data Abstractions
Kokkos	C++ Abstraction	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
OpenMP	Directives	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-
OpenACC	Directives	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	-
CUDA	Extension	(X)	-	(X)	X	-	X	X	-
OpenCL	Extension	(X)	-	(X)	X	-	X	X	-
C++AMP	Extension	X	-	X	-	-	X	X	-
Raja	C++ Abstraction	X	X	X	(X)	-	-	-	-
TBB	C++ Abstraction	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-
C++17	Language	X	-	-	-	(X)	X	(X)	(X)
Fortran2008	Language	X	-	-	-	-	X	(X)	-

SYCL

- Open standard developed by the Khronos group
- Generalized back-end architecture
 - *Supporting OpenCL, HIP, CUDA, LevelZero (Intel)*
- Data parallel kernels with execution organized by a task graph
- Two different memory models (buffer-accessor, Unified Shared Memory)

DPC++ (Intel SYCL) example

```
void dpcpp_code(int* a, int* b, int* c) {  
    // Setting up a device queue  
    queue q;  
    // Setup buffers for input and output vectors  
    buffer buf_a(a, range<1>(N));  
    buffer buf_b(b, range<1>(N));  
    buffer buf_c(c, range<1>(N));  
    //Submit command group function object to the queue  
    q.submit([&](handler &h){  
        //Create device accessors to buffers allocated in global memory  
        accessor A(buf_a, h, read_only);  
        accessor B(buf_b, h, read_only);  
        accessor C(buf_c, h, write_only);  
        //Specify the device kernel body as a lambda function  
        h.parallel_for(range<1>(N), [=](auto i){  
            C[i] = A[i] + B[i];  
        });  
    });  
}
```

Step 1: create a device queue
(developer can specify a device type via device selector or use default selector)

Step 2: create buffers
(represent both host and device memory)

Step 3: submit a command group for
(asynchronous) execution

Step 4: create accessors
describing how buffer is used on
the device

Step 5: specify kernel function and
launch parameters (e.g. group size)

Step 6: specify code to run on
the device

Kernel invocations
are executed in
parallel

Kernel is invoked
for each element of
the range

Kernel invocation
has access to the
invocation id

Done!

The results are copied to vector c at buf_c buffer destruction

SYCL Example: Graph of Asynchronous Executions

```
myQueue.submit([&](handler& cgh) {  
    auto A = a.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto B = b.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto C = c.get_access<access::mode::discardwrite>(cgh);  
    cgh.parallel_for<class add1>( range<2>{N, M},  
        [=](id<2> index) { C[index] = A[index] + B[index]; });  
});
```

```
myQueue.submit([&](handler& cgh) {  
    auto A = a.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto C = c.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto D = d.get_access<access::mode::write>(cgh);  
    cgh.parallel_for<class add2>( range<2>{P, Q},  
        [=](id<2> index) { D[index] = A[index] + C[index]; });  
});
```

```
myQueue.submit([&](handler& cgh) {  
    auto A = a.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto D = d.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto E = e.get_access<access::mode::write>(cgh);  
    cgh.parallel_for<class add3>( range<2>{S, T},  
        [=](id<2> index) { E[index] = A[index] + D[index]; });  
});
```


SYCL Example: Graph of Asynchronous Executions

```
myQueue.submit([&](handler& cgh) {  
    auto A = a.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto B = b.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto C = c.get_access<access::mode::discardwrite>(cgh);  
    cgh.parallel_for<class add1>( range<2>{N, M},  
        [=](id<2> index) { C[index] = A[index] + B[index]; });  
});
```

```
myQueue.submit([&](handler& cgh) {  
    auto A = a.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto D = d.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto E = e.get_access<access::mode::discardwrite>(cgh);  
    cgh.parallel_for<class add2>( range<2>{P, Q},  
        [=](id<2> index) { E[index] = A[index] + D[index]; });  
});
```

```
myQueue.submit([&](handler& cgh) {  
    auto C = c.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto E = e.get_access<access::mode::read>(cgh);  
    auto F = f.get_access<access::mode::discardwrite>(cgh);  
    cgh.parallel_for<class add3>( range<2>{S, T},  
        [=](id<2> index) { F[index] = C[index] + E[index]; });  
});
```


- SYCL queues are out-of-order by default – data dependencies order kernel executions
- Will also be able to use in-order queue policies to simplify porting

Intel® DPC++ Compatibility Tool

Minimizes Code Migration Time

Assists developers migrating code written in CUDA to DPC++ once, generating human readable code wherever possible

~80-90% of code typically migrates automatically

Inline comments are provided to help developers finish porting the application

Intel DPC ++ Compatibility Tool Usage Flow

[Optimization Notice](#)

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Some experiments with SYCL: gradient based image processing

Intel OneAPI DevCloud

CPU: 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-11900KB @ 3.30GHz

GPU: Intel® Xeon® E-2176 P630 processors

Data:

- [Original](#)
- [Results v1](#)
- [Results v2](#)

“Semi”-automatic translation CUDA-SYCL

CUDA kernels

```
float_to_char<<<numBlocks_mult, threadsPerBlock>>>(dimx, dimy, _d_xvec, _d_sol_data);
```

```
q.parallel_for(  
    sycl::nd_range<3>(numBlocks_mult * threadsPerBlock, threadsPerBlock),  
    [=](sycl::nd_item<3> item_ct1) {  
        float_to_char(dimx, dimy, _d_xvec, _d_sol_data, item_ct1);  
    });
```

CUBLAS

```
rho = cublasSdot(N, (float *)_d_p, 1, (float *)_d_p, 1);
```

```
oneapi::mkl::blas::column_major::dot(q, N, (float *)_d_p, 1, (float *)_d_p, 1, &rho).wait();
```

There is still some work left to do

- SYCL is a promising solution but still in its infancy
 - *one API but multiple implementations:*
 - ComputeCPP (codeplay)
 - Intel SYCL
 - triSYCL
 - hipSYCL
 - *Users have to learn yet another programming model (but now can also rely on translation tools)*
- Portability of code does not necessarily mean portability of performance
 - *optimal performance might still require manual optimizations*

Things will still be messy...

Example: optimizing (e.g., all-to-all) collective operations on different devices might require completely different approaches

CPU (MPI)

GPU (NCCL MPI)

THANK YOU

